

Online Surrogate-assisted Nuclear Core Optimization for Enhanced Computational Efficiency

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803888

ABSTRACT

Reactor core design optimization involves computationally expensive, multiobjective trade-offs among safety, performance, and cost metrics. This study applies the NSGA-III algorithm to optimize the fuel assembly enrichments and burnable absorber configuration of a NuScale-like small modular reactor core, aiming to minimize fuel-levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) and peak boron concentration while maximizing fuel effective full power years (EFPY). To reduce the high computational cost of CASMO4/SIMULATE3 simulations, an online surrogate-assisted NSGA-III (SA-NSGA-III) framework employing a feedforward neural network surrogate with adaptive sampling is introduced. Across ten optimization runs, baseline NSGA-III required 41000 equilibrium-cycle evaluations, whereas SA-NSGA-III achieved comparable Pareto-front quality using 25960 evaluations, reducing the computational cost by 36.68%. The surrogate-assisted approach proposed here did not require a pre-trained surrogate model and also decreased constraint-breaching simulations while maintaining effective exploration and convergence. These results demonstrate that online surrogate assistance can substantially lower the computational cost of reactor design optimization without degrading accuracy, highlighting its promise for broader nuclear design applications.

Keywords: Reactor Core Optimization, Multiobjective Optimization, Surrogate Modeling, NSGA-III, Small Modular Reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

Optimization problems are common in engineering and are often defined as computationally expensive black-box functions with no accessible gradient information [1]. In such cases, population-based optimization methods are widely used for their robustness and gradient-free operation [2]. These methods are especially effective in black-box settings where analytical models are unavailable. Since no method consistently outperforms others across all problems [3], comparative studies remain a common practice.

Many real-world engineering problems involve multiple, conflicting objectives such as safety, cost, and efficiency. While scalarization techniques like weighted sums can approximate trade-offs by repeated single-objective optimizations, dedicated multiobjective algorithms are more effective. Algorithms such as NSGA-II [4] and NSGA-III [5] directly construct Pareto-optimal solution sets using non-dominated sorting and diversity preservation techniques.

When simulation costs are high, surrogate-assisted optimization can reduce computational demands by replacing expensive model evaluations with predictive approximations. These models are trained on initial input-output data and used to guide further search. Gaussian Processes are often used in low-dimensional problems, while neural networks are preferred in higher dimensions due to their scalability [6]. Despite the demonstrated potential of surrogate-assisted methods, their practical limits in design optimization remain largely unexplored, particularly in determining how much computational cost can be reduced in nuclear core optimization without degrading model accuracy. *In this paper, the term surrogate model refers to an **online surrogate** that is trained on-the-fly during the optimization process, rather*

than a pre-trained surrogate that requires running tens of thousands of simulations in advance—an approach that often limits practical usefulness.

In nuclear engineering, optimization is used for reactor core design, fuel cycle planning, and power system control. Objectives typically include maximizing fuel burnup and operational lifetime, while minimizing power peaking factors and fuel cost [7]. Early studies evaluated the feasibility of small modular reactors (SMRs) in terms of scalability, licensing challenges, and deployment costs, highlighting both the opportunities and the barriers [8]. Recent developments in SMR technology have renewed interest in efficient and cost-effective core design approaches. In this work, a population-based multiobjective algorithm, NSGA-III, is employed to optimize the assembly enrichments of a NuScale-like core model [9], both with and without online surrogate assistance. The objectives include maximizing fuel effective full power years (EFPY) while minimizing the core boron concentration and fuel-levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) [10].

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Investigated Core Design

The NuScale-like core model developed by Fridman et al. [9] is used as a reference in this work. As shown in Figure 1, this model includes seven assembly types (A01, A02, B01, B02, C01, C02, C03) with U-235 enrichments of 1.5%, 1.6%, 2.5%, 2.6%, 4.05%, 4.55%, and 2.6% by weight. Only C02 assemblies include 8% Gd₂O₃ burnable absorber (BA) rods. The core follows a three-cycle fixed shuffling scheme: A0X locations are refueled with B0X assemblies, B0X are replaced by C0X, and fresh fuel is loaded into C0X positions. C0X assemblies are always fresh in each cycle.

Figure 1. Left: Assembly names in the NuScale-like core layout. Right: Pin powers from SIMULATE3 results of the NuScale-like core at BOL under CZP conditions.

A deterministic model of this core is created in SIMULATE3. Simulations reproduce core behavior closely: the beginning-of-life (BOL) cold zero power (CZP) reactivity with 1000 ppm boron concentration is calculated as 2301 pcm, compared to 2768 pcm in the reference. Power distributions and core parameters match well with the published results. Additional core metrics are extracted and given in Table I. The metrics show that the published design [9] exceeds the $F\Delta H$ limit of 1.5. Optimization is therefore needed to bring safety parameters within acceptable ranges while improving performance.

The same fuel shuffling scheme as the reference paper is preserved during optimization to avoid exponential growth in search space. Equilibrium cycle is observed in the 5th cycle of the simulations. The

core average exposure difference between the end of cycles 5 and 6 is observed as 0.335% and the future simulations in this paper have used 5th cycle as the equilibrium cycle.

Table I. SIMULATE3 reference results of the NuScale-like design during operation in the first five cycles.

F_q	$F\Delta H$	Max. Boron Conc. (ppm)	Eq. Cycle Fuel EFPY	Eq. Cycle Fuel LCOE (\$/MWh)
2.279	1.561	1265.2	4.9114	14.6349

2.2. Optimization Process

The optimization problem has eight discrete input variables and three objectives, subject to two safety-related constraints. The input variables are the enrichment values of the seven assemblies and the configuration of BA rod distribution. Enrichment values are varied within ± 0.4 wt% of their nominal levels, discretized in 0.02 wt% steps. This results in 41 possible values per assembly. BA distribution is selected from four configurations, varying the placement and number of rods in C01 and C02 assemblies. Precompiling cross-section libraries for these discrete combinations allows the use of a fixed CASMO4/SIMULATE3 cross-section library during optimization, avoiding expensive recompiling.

The total design space includes approximately 7.79×10^{11} combinations. To explore this space, NSGA-III is used with a population size of 100 and 40 generations, totaling 4100 function evaluations (including initialization). **Equilibrium cycle SIMULATE3 simulations (referred to as fitness evaluations)** take approximately 30 seconds per case, parallelized over 20 processes due to Studsvik academic licensing limits. Three optimization objectives are selected to create meaningful trade-offs:

- **Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE):** Calculated following the formulation of Seurin and Shirvan [10], the LCOE represents the core-level economic performance. The model accounts for fuel-related costs, including ore, enrichment, waste, and wet annular burnable absorber (WABA) expenses, as well as discount rates and levelization periods. Since the contribution of initial cycles to the overall LCOE diminishes over time, the calculation is performed using the equilibrium-cycle exposure values of discharged assemblies (C01, C02 and C03) and WABA cost is excluded from the equilibrium-cycle LCOE to represent the long-term steady-state operation.
- **Maximum Soluble Boron Concentration:** Boron concentration influences moderator feedback coefficients. High concentrations (>1500 ppm) are undesirable due to the potential for positive reactivity coefficients. The reference core exhibits a peak boron concentration of 1099 ppm at the beginning of the first cycle and a maximum of 1265 ppm within the first five cycles.
- **Fuel Effective Full Power Years (EFPY):** A key metric for fuel utilization, used to evaluate irradiation exposure and related performance limits. Since each assembly operates for three cycles, fuel EFPY is estimated as three times the equilibrium cycle length.

The optimization seeks to minimize LCOE and peak boron concentration while maximizing fuel EFPY. Constraints are enforced to maintain F_q and $F\Delta H$ within standard design limits (2.49 and 1.5, respectively). The core design is discarded if either F_q or $F\Delta H$ breaches the constraints.

NSGA-III is configured with a crossover probability of 0.7 using a blending crossover operator, a mutation probability of 0.3, and a population size of 100 individuals. Convergence is typically observed within 40 generations. **To limit computation time, the number of generations is fixed at 40 for both the baseline NSGA-III and surrogate-assisted NSGA-III (SA-NSGA-III) runs.**

2.3. Surrogate-assisted Optimization

To reduce the computational cost of optimization, a neural network surrogate-assisted optimization is also evaluated. The model is trained on initial samples generated by the Sobol sampling method and the data generated by the fitness function in each generation. Surrogate-assisting enables more

efficient exploration in computationally expensive fitness functions. The surrogate-assisting framework is positioned between the optimization algorithm and the fitness function. The model follows five steps: surrogate evaluation, individual selection, error calculation, model retraining, returning the requests. In each generation, the optimization algorithm requests candidate points from the surrogate model. If no model exists, the initial data sampling is performed and the surrogate is trained. A permanent test set is also established from random evaluations.

The candidate points requested by the optimization algorithm are first evaluated by the surrogate model. Based on surrogate predictions, a subset of points is selected for fitness function evaluation. The best candidates are selected from the surrogate predictions by using an individual performance score, S_x , which combines Pareto rank, crowding distance, and reference distance, as defined in Equation (1):

$$S_x = \left(1 - \frac{\text{rank}_x}{\max(\text{rank}_y)}\right) + \frac{\text{CD}_x + \text{RD}_x}{2(\max(\text{rank}_y) + 1)}, \quad (1)$$

where $y \in [1, \dots, N_i]$ denotes the index of all individuals in population i , rank_x is the Pareto rank of individual x (lower is better), $\text{CD}_x \in [0, 1]$ is the normalized crowding distance in the same rank, and $\text{RD}_x \in [0, 1]$ is the normalized reference distance from the nadir point.

After the selected points are evaluated in the fitness function, the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) between surrogate predictions and fitness evaluations is recorded as local error. The permanent test set is used to calculate a global MAPE metric. After error estimation, the points run in the fitness function are appended to the training dataset and the model is retrained.

Both the points evaluated in the fitness function and the surrogate predictions are returned to the optimization algorithm. The SA-NSGA-III setup uses a dynamic evaluation ratio, starting from one and decreasing as the model becomes confident, meaning that fewer points are directly evaluated in the fitness function than requested by the optimizer. This reduced evaluation ratio significantly lowers the computational cost of reactor core optimization while preserving the fidelity of the search process.

The surrogate-assisted optimization is configured with **constant 200 surrogate model evaluations per generation and 100 true fitness function evaluations per generation**. Purpose of implementing the SA-NSGA-III is to decrease the number of fitness function evaluations. In each generation, 20% of the fitness evaluations are selected via adaptive sampling, while the remaining 80% are selected based on the surrogate model's predicted pareto front. Adaptive sampling is performed using the kNN-Residual-Error method. The permanent test set is sampled with 50 points. The implemented surrogate model is a feedforward neural network with three hidden layers, each containing 50 neurons, using a learning rate of 10^{-3} , batch size of 8, and trained for 50 epochs per generation.

The dynamic evaluation strategy is initialized with an error threshold of 1%. At each step, the allowable error limit is halved, and the evaluation ratio is reduced by 0.1 of its initial value. The evaluation ratio is bounded below by a minimum value of 0.3 (30 fitness function evaluations) to ensure sufficient fitness function evaluations for maintaining optimization reliability. The minimum dynamic evaluation ratio is reached when local and global MAPE reaches to 0.0078125%.

Although Gaussian Processes are widely regarded as a reliable surrogate modeling approach, they are not suitable for this application due to the large number of training points and the need for retraining in each generation. As a result, after initial test with Gaussian processes, a neural network surrogate is selected for its scalability and efficiency under high-dimensional, data-intensive conditions.

3. RESULTS

The results presented in this section evaluate the performance of NSGA-III optimization applied to the NuScale-like core design, both with and without surrogate assistance. The primary objectives (fuel

Figure 2. Points evaluated in the fitness function by each algorithm. Exploration performances of both methods can be observed in this plot. The points that breach the constraints are excluded from the plot. 1646 NSGA-III points (out of 4100) and 1765 SA-NSGA-III points (out of 2660) are displayed. EFY objective is negated in the plots to make all 2D plots a minimization problem, where lower left side corresponds to better objective values.

LCOE and peak boron concentration minimization, fuel EFY maximization) are used to assess the quality of the optimized designs and to analyze trade-offs between economic and safety-related performance. Unless stated otherwise, all reported results correspond to equilibrium-cycle conditions.

3.1. NSGA-III Results

NSGA-III produces a highly detailed Pareto front, demonstrating the algorithm's ability to explore the constrained objective space effectively. The resulting solutions satisfy all safety constraints. All three objectives exhibit clear trade-offs, as shown in the pairwise 2D plots in Figure 2. This confirms that the selected objectives introduce conflicting performance targets, resulting in a well-defined Pareto front rather than a single optimal solution.

The physical design limits imposed by the constraints are clearly visible in Figure 2. These limits define the boundary of the Pareto front, as the optimizer cannot cross the regulatory thresholds set for the reactor core. Consequently, individuals located along the constraint boundary are also part of the Pareto-optimal front.

3.2. Surrogate-assisted NSGA-III (SA-NSGA-III) Results

SA-NSGA-III achieves comparable exploration of the objective space while requiring substantially fewer fitness function evaluations. The dynamically adjusted evaluation ratio converges to a final value of 0.5, demonstrating that integrating the surrogate model between NSGA-III and the fitness function maintains exploration capability while improving efficiency. The surrogate model effectively generates additional high-quality samples in a virtual objective space without increasing the number of costly evaluations. As a result, the frequency of true fitness function calls decreases progressively.

The ratio of constraint-breaching evaluations is significantly lower for the SA-NSGA-III method. As shown in Figure 2, NSGA-III performed 4100 fitness evaluations, whereas SA-NSGA-III required only 2660. Among these, 1646 NSGA-III evaluations and 1765 SA-NSGA-III evaluations satisfied all constraints. This corresponds to non-breaching ratios of 40.14% for NSGA-III and 66.35% for SA-NSGA-III, indicating that surrogate assistance effectively guides the search toward feasible regions and reduces constraint violations, eliminating more than one third of the unfeasible simulations.

When the dynamic evaluation ratio is applied, the number of fitness function evaluations in SA-NSGA-III decreases at generations 3, 5, 8, 16, and 33, as the surrogate's local and global errors fall below 1%, 0.5%, 0.25%, 0.125%, and 0.0625%, respectively. This trend is shown in Figure 3. It is possible to further

Figure 3. Evolution of local and global surrogate model errors with generation number (left). The dynamic evaluation size of SA-NSGA-III is shown alongside (right), illustrating that fitness evaluations are reduced as model error decreases. MAPE of current population is recorded as local error. MAPE of permanent test set is recorded as global error.

reduce the evaluation ratio in SA-NSGA-III to lower the computational cost of the method. However, disabling all fitness function evaluations and relying solely on the surrogate model leads to unreliable model predictions.

Even with an adaptive sampling ratio of 0.2 (meaning that 20% of the evaluations are reserved for improving surrogate accuracy) the reduced number of optimization point evaluations remains sufficient to extract high-quality core designs. As illustrated in Figure 3, during the latter half of the optimization, SA-NSGA-III evaluates only 60 points per generation, with 48 of these drawn for the optimization points. Despite this reduced sampling, the surrogate-assisted algorithm successfully produces a highly detailed Pareto front comparable to the baseline method.

3.3. Method Comparison

The NSGA-III and SA-NSGA-III optimizations were each repeated with 10 random seeds to assess result consistency. The NSGA-III method required 41000 SIMULATE3 equilibrium-cycle evaluations, corresponding to a total runtime of 19.08 hours, whereas SA-NSGA-III completed the optimization in 25960 evaluations and 12.55 hours.

To compare the performance of the optimization approaches, the solutions discovered by each algorithm are recorded cumulatively across generations. At every generation, the recursive N -dimensional hypervolume (HV) indicator is computed over the cumulative Pareto front [11]. This metric quantifies the portion of objective space dominated by the Pareto front relative to a reference point, defined as the Nadir point (i.e., the component-wise worst values across all objectives).

In addition to HV, the normalized sum of objectives is used as a secondary performance indicator, showing whether a method achieves a lower combined objective value than the other. While HV captures the overall spread and convergence of the Pareto front, the normalized objective sum provides a simpler, single-point comparison of representative designs, complementing the multiobjective analysis. The mean and standard deviations of indicators are shown in Figure 4 for each generation of the 10 optimization runs of NSGA-III and SA-NSGA-III methods.

In Figure 4, NSGA-III achieves a slightly higher HV indicator value. This result is expected as NSGA-III performs 57.94% more fitness function evaluations than SA-NSGA-III. More evaluations result in a more diverse result set, resulting in more coverage in objective space and a higher HV indicator. However,

Figure 4. Mean and standard deviation of performance indicators across 10 optimization runs for NSGA-III (blue) and SA-NSGA-III (yellow). Solid lines represent the mean values, and shaded regions indicate standard deviations. The left plot shows the cumulative hypervolume evolution, while the right plot shows the best normalized objective sum per generation.

SA-NSGA-III attains a slightly better normalized objective sum with substantially fewer evaluations. By reducing the number of constraint-breaching simulations and prioritizing core designs predicted to yield optimal outcomes by the surrogate model, the surrogate-assisted approach achieves improved convergence characteristics while requiring 36.68% fewer fitness function evaluations.

To enable a direct comparison between the two methods and illustrate representative practical outcomes for the industry, the parameters of the NSGA-III-optimized core and the SA-NSGA-III-optimized core corresponding to the best normalized objective sum values are presented in Table II. It can be easily seen that the most optimal designs found by both methods are very comparable, with SA-NSGA-III requiring much fewer fitness evaluations.

Table II. Design variables and objective results for the best-performing NSGA-III and SA-NSGA-III optimized NuScale-like core configurations. First 2 rows only include the solutions with minimum normalized objective sum value, last 2 rows include solutions with minimum normalized objective and constraint sum value.

Method	Enrichments (%)							BA Loc.	Objectives				
	A01	A02	B01	B02	C01	C02	C03		LCOE	Boron	EFPY	Fq	FΔH
NSGA-III	1.82	1.98	2.36	2.2	4.11	4.15	2.2	C02	14.4398	1243.3	4.8674	2.153	1.480
SA-NSGA	1.9	1.92	2.28	2.2	4.11	4.15	2.2	C02	14.4326	1252.5	4.8643	2.148	1.477
NSGA-III	1.88	2.0	2.28	2.76	3.95	4.15	2.44	C02	14.5375	1435	4.7158	1.990	1.372
SA-NSGA	1.88	2.0	2.54	2.38	4.05	4.15	2.52	C02	14.5319	1375.8	4.8381	2.012	1.388

4. CONCLUSION

This study applied the NSGA-III and online surrogate-assisted NSGA-III (SA-NSGA-III) algorithms to the multiobjective optimization of a NuScale-like reactor core, targeting the minimization of fuel LCOE and boron concentration and the maximization of fuel EFPY. Both methods successfully identified feasible designs within the regulatory constraints and produced well-defined Pareto fronts illustrating the inherent trade-offs between economic and safety-related performance metrics.

The online surrogate-assisted approach demonstrated a significant reduction in computational cost while maintaining comparable optimization quality. By integrating a feedforward neural network surrogate model with adaptive error monitoring, SA-NSGA-III effectively reduced the number of re-

quired fitness function evaluations by more than one-third, without degrading Pareto front fidelity. The method also showed improved convergence efficiency by guiding the search toward feasible regions and avoiding constraint violations.

These findings highlight the potential of surrogate-assisted multiobjective optimization in nuclear design applications, where simulation cost remains a major barrier. However, the limits of surrogate-assisted approaches—particularly their performance under highly nonlinear or discontinuous objective spaces—remain open research questions. Future work will focus on extending this framework to coupled physics problems, uncertainty quantification, and large-scale reactor optimization tasks to further assess the scalability and generalizability of the surrogate-assisted approach.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is sponsored by the Department of Energy Office of Nuclear Energy's Distinguished Early Career Program (Award number: DE-NE0009424), which is administered by the Nuclear Energy University Program.

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